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Exploring the role of plant doctor quizzes and social media on plant health services in Uganda: Focus on the Plantwise Uganda telegram in Uganda

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EXPLORING THE OF ROLE OF PLANT DOCTOR QUIZZES AND SOCIAL MEDIA
ON PLANT HEALTH SERVICES IN UGANDA: FOCUS ON THE PLANTWISE
UGANDA TELEGRAM IN UGANDA

A Thesis Presented

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This programme was co-organised by the Institute of Biology (IBIOL) of the University of Neuchâtel and CABI under the direction of Prof. Ted Turlings, University of Neuchâtel, and Dr. Ulrich Kuhlmann, CABI. It took place at CABI in Delemont, Canton of Jura, Switzerland,

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Abstract

The use of social media and other digital sites are increasingly becoming integrated into many of people's daily lives. With the advancement in the digital technology and the need to harness the potential of ICT, CABI supported the formation of Plantwise Uganda telegram a social media group that not only links the plant doctors to local diagnostic support but also connects plant doctors with the UK-based Plantwise Diagnostic and Advisory Services for further diagnostic support services. CABI further introduced the plant doctor quiz as an innovation to provide training through the social media groups.

The main objective of the study, therefore, was to explore the role of social media with emphasis on Plantwise telegram and plant doctor quizzes in the plant health knowledge and information transfer in Uganda.

Online survey questionnaires were used to collect the data. Two questionnaires were used; one on social media and plant health and the second on plant doctor quizzes and plant health.

Results show that Plantwise Uganda telegram membership range from field extension officers, academia and diagnostic specialists' majority of which have tertiary education and trained by Plantwise which enables them to support the plant health diagnostics and advisory services.

The study revealed that many plant doctors are not aware of the existence of the Plantwise Uganda telegram and its services. Other than Plantwise Uganda telegram, plant doctors mostly use WhatsApp and Facebook to discuss plant health issues. Multi-platform use is high.

Education level, Plantwise training and gender influenced the frequency and level of confidence to give advice on the telegram. Education level did not influence the frequency of asking for advice from the Plantwise Uganda telegram.

About the plant doctor quiz, study findings reveal that plant doctor quiz is an important learning tool for plant doctors. Plant doctors like to receive the quizzes via emails, WhatsApp and Telegram Inboxes other than posting on Plantwise Uganda telegram.

High internet costs, poor network connectivity and nonexistence of internet connection are the reasons that prevent plant doctor from doing and partially filling the quizzes they start. Other plant doctors with the capacity to take the quiz miss taking quizzes because they consider it not a priority.

Popularizing the Plantwise Uganda telegram and plant doctor quiz should be prioritised by plant health actors if they are to be maximumly utilized to support the knowledge sharing and transfer on plant health. This can be done through awareness programs/campaigns, social media literacy training programs and workshops to help plant doctors and other plant health actors understand and use the social media and plant doctor quizzes better.

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List of Acronyms

ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
MAAIF	Ministry of Agriculture Animal Industry and Fisheries
UBOS	Uganda Bureau of Statistics
CABI	Center for Agriculture and Biosciences International
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
MDAs	Government Ministries, Departments and Agencies
DAS	Diagnostic and Advisory Services
NITA-U	National Information and Technology Authority-Uganda
MoICT	Ministry of Information and Communications Technology

1.0 Introduction

1.1. The social media concept

The use of social media and other digital sites are increasingly becoming integrated into many of people's daily lives (Barau & Afrad 2017). Social media like WhatsApp, Facebook, Telegram, LinkedIn, YouTube among others have become mainstream avenues for information sharing and networking (Kamp 2016, Osterrieder, 2013, Iroeze et al., 2012). In their study, Yoo- Lee and Sin (2011), pointed out that social media is gaining popularity and plays an important role as an information source.

Baruah (2012) defines the term social media as the use of web- based and mobile technologies to turn communication into an interactive dialogue. Constantinides and fountain (2008) says that social media concept is built on what is known as Web 2.0 defined as a collection of open-source, interactive and user-controlled online applications expanding the experiences, knowledge and market power of the users as respondents in business and social processes.

Web 2.0 technologies enabled the emergence of social media. Social media can generally refer to a group of online applications that enable users to generate and share their opinions and experiences in forms of pictures, voice messages, songs and text messages among others. Kaplan & Haenlein (2010), defines social media as a group of applications which is based on ideological and technological foundations of web 2.0 that allows the creation and exchange of user generated content.

According to Mayfield (2008), all social media sites have the following fundamental characteristics: participation, conversationality, connectedness, community and openness.

Social media sites can be categorized in several ways: social networking sites (SNS), blogs, microblogs, content sharing sites (CSS), social bookmarking sites, wikis, podcasts and forums. (Constantinides & Fountain, 2008, Mayfield 2008, Kocak & Oyman 2012). The social media phenomenon in view of the above background, presents new opportunities for plant doctors, extension officers, farmers, researchers and many other plant health actors to actively engage, share opinion as well as interact in direct and personal ways

1.2. Use of social media in Uganda

The government of Uganda appreciates the importance of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) in economic development and takes initiatives to attract investments in the sector (Gillwald & Tusubira et al., 2019). In 2013 the government recognized the role of social media as a communication tool and directed the Ministry of Information and Communications Technology (MoICT) to ensure that Government Ministries, Departments and Agencies (MDAs) open a Twitter and Facebook account to enhance communication and encourage public participation in the governing process. (NITA-U 2013).

In the same year, the National Information Technology Authority Uganda (NITA-U) prepared a social media guide to support government Ministries, Departments and Agencies (MDAs) to effectively and securely use social media. The National Information Technology survey report (2018), reveals that 92.2% of MDAs were using social media and most MDAs (98%) used Facebook followed by Twitter (85.7%). The reports highlight a growing importance of social media as a platform to convey information to the people and to encourage the participation of the citizens.

1.3. Use of social media and plant doctor quiz by Plantwise to support the provision of plant health services

Plantwise is a global program led by Center for Agriculture and Biosciences International (CABI), to increase food security and improve livelihoods by reducing crop losses. Plantwise works alongside the local extension services, Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) and other key stakeholders in the plant health system to provide small holder farmers with access to advisory services from plant clinics (Danielsen and Matsiko 2016, Wright et al 2016).

With the advancement in the digital technology and the need to harness the potential of ICT, CABI develops and uses ICT-based tools to support and improve plant doctors' technical capacities. i.e. Plant doctor simulation game, Plantwise Factsheet Library App, Offline Knowledge Bank amongst others (Thakur and Beverley *et al.*, 2018). The social media groups and the plant doctor quiz are among the new ICT-based innovations to support the plant doctors.

CABI often supports the establishment of social media groups hosted by (Telegram, WhatsApp, Facebook, WeChat, etc.) that not only link the plant doctors to local diagnostic support but also connects them with the UK-based Plantwise Diagnostic and Advisory Services (DAS) for further diagnostic support services. The plant doctor quiz is an innovation to provide training through the social media groups. Plant doctor quiz complements the conventional plant doctor training and provides an ongoing capacity building through an enjoyable and rewarding approach (Plantwise Annual report 2018).

1.4. Plantwise Uganda telegram

In Uganda, the main group that was established is the Plantwise Uganda hosted by Telegram software. It was formed when the WhatsApp Electronic-plant clinic group was converted to a supergroup Plantwise Uganda. Plant doctors receive diagnostic support when they post photos of plant problems on the Plantwise Uganda telegram from fellow plant doctors, subject matter specialists and the UK- Diagnostic Advisory services. Plant doctors also use the social media group to share information and experiences on plant health issues in their plant clinics.

The National Plantwise Uganda telegram regularly facilitates quick sharing of queries on pest outbreaks, spread of pests and sharing of management options among members who in turn disseminate to farmers and extension staff (Plantwise Annual report 2017).

1.5. Plant doctor quiz.

Plant doctor quiz is amongst one of the several innovative learning tools by CABI under Plantwise to support the successful running of plant clinics by continuously supporting plant doctors with knowledge and improving their diagnostic skills.

The plant doctor quiz was started in August 2018 by CABI to allow plant doctors test their plant health knowledge, refresh their diagnostic skills and acquire new knowledge. The test results from the quiz are monitored by CABI to help improve the quiz design and plant doctor training modules.

Plant doctors receive the quiz with ten questions on a monthly basis with links to the survey monkey site shared via the Plantwise Uganda telegram and email. The quizzes are designed in form of photos and multiple-choice questions. The plant doctor can assess him/herself after giving a response to the quiz questions. This is possible because, when a response is entered, immediately the correct answer is given with explanations on why the option given is either right or wrong. The application also allows members to share the quiz questions by forwarding the quiz link to other social media sites like Facebook and WhatsApp.

1.6. Statement of the problem

According to CABI, there are 40 out of 505 plant doctors from Uganda who have answered the plant doctor quiz and there are other records of plant doctors who have answered the quiz anonymously which makes data interpretation difficult.

The success of the plant doctor quizzes has further been hampered by factors such as; respondents' failure to finish the quiz they start, completely discontinuing from responding to the quizzes, responding to some quizzes while missing others and low number of plant doctors responding to the quiz. The purpose of this study is to establish the factors that cause; partial finishing of the quizzes, factors that make plant doctors miss doing a quiz, and factors that influence the accessibility of the quizzes to plant doctors.

Literature shows that social media has the potential to play an important role in plant health knowledge and information sharing. However, research on the use of social media in Plantwise is on-going and gaps still exist in knowledge on how social media is used, the constraints and incentives to its use within Plantwise. It is important that more studies are carried out to identify ways how social media can best be utilized as part of a communication tool on all aspects of plant health systems.

This study therefore provides fact -based information on the role of social media with emphasis on Plantwise Uganda telegram and explores its role as a tool for knowledge sharing as used by plant doctors and other plant health actors in Uganda.

1.7. Justification of the study

Using social media to promote plant pest and disease management is a worthwhile strategy. Social media plays a unique and important role in the communication and information sharing among many plant health actors. The results will generate important data to support the use of social media as a communication tool in Plantwise.

The knowledge generated from studying the plant doctors quiz will be important in improving the plant doctor training and the design of the plant doctor quiz.

The new information generated from the study will stimulate further insight that will foster continued inquiries into the subjects.

1.8. Overall Objectives

The aim of this study is to explore the role of;

- ✚ social media and,
- ✚ plant doctor quizzes on plant health knowledge and information sharing in Uganda

1.8.1. *Specific objectives:*

- I. To determine the categories of members on Plantwise Uganda telegram.
- II. To assess the status of subscription to Plantwise Uganda telegram in relation Plantwise training.
- III. To determine other social media sites where plant health actors interact on plant health issues.
- IV. To assess the roles and interaction of plant doctors on social media sites in relation to seeking or giving advice on plant health.
- V. To examine the factors that influence the accessibility of plant doctor quizzes to the different plant doctors.
- VI. To determine reasons why plant doctors do not complete answering the quiz they start.
- VII. To examine factors that prevent plant doctors from answering the quizzes.

2.0. Materials and Methods

2.1. Data collection

The population under study were Ugandan plant doctors who use the plant doctor quiz, Plantwise Uganda telegram members and other Agricultural Extension Officers who were trained by Plantwise who use social media especially WhatsApp.

2.1.1. Literature review

A search for published literature was conducted, to find: the role of social media in plant health services, the use of quizzes as a learning tool and their role in knowledge sharing and transfer. In this desk review, internet search engines such as Google scholar, Google and CABI direct were used to find online resources. Activity reports on Plantwise Uganda telegram and plant doctor quiz from CABI were accessed. The data formed the preliminary step in gaining insights into what the study entailed and used in setting a good background for the study.

2.1.2. Online survey using questionnaires

Two data collection instruments were used. The first questionnaire was on the use of Plantwise Uganda telegram or other social media sites (Appendix 1) and the second questionnaire was on the use of plant doctor quiz in plant health knowledge sharing and transfer (Appendix 2). Online sources (Brace 2018 and Siniscalco & Auriat 2005), plant doctor quiz July 2019, Plantwise Uganda telegram chats and the study objectives informed the design and questions that were asked.

Lists of Plantwise Uganda telegram users and plant doctor quiz users that were availed by CABI and that of plant doctors in Uganda availed by the Plantwise National data manager, were used for selection of the respondents.

To validate the survey tools, pre-testing of the questionnaires prior to the final survey was done on 8 MAS-ICM 2019 students and 2 Agricultural Extension Officers from Kayunga district local government, Uganda.

The dissemination of the questionnaires was done using a weblink from Google forms-a web based application that supports online survey. The survey was done online since the use of social media and plant doctor quiz requires the use of internet.

2.1.3. Selection of respondents for the plant doctor quiz and social media

Table 1. Shows number of respondents and how they were contacted for the study

Questionnaire	Method of dissemination of the questionnaire	Number of respondents contacted		
		Male	Female	
Social media questionnaire	Plantwise Uganda telegram	50	20	70
	WhatsApp	52	28	80
	Total	102	48	150
Plant doctor quiz questionnaire	Email	32	7	39
	Plantwise Uganda telegram	16	15	31
	Total	48	22	70

2.1.3.1. Selection of respondents for the plant doctor quiz.

A total 70 plant doctors were selected to participate in the plant doctor quiz survey. 39 were quiz users while the remaining 31 were non quiz users. The thirty one non quiz user were randomly selected from a list Plantwise Uganda telegram members. The survey instrument was designed to collect basic demographic data and consisted mostly of multiple choice questions with 2 questions that required addition of more information in case the answer was a "yes". These questions were about giving reasons why plant doctors partially filled the quizzes they had started, and the other question was about reasons what prevented them from doing a plant doctor quiz.

To examine the factors that influence the accessibility of quizzes to the plant doctors. Participants ranked attributes that relate to plant doctor quiz using a 5 point Likert scale. Responses were sought on how; communication channels used to share the quiz, the frequency of doing the quiz, the number of quiz questions and including names on the quiz influence the plant doctor's participation in the plant doctor quiz.

2.1.3.2. Selection of respondents for social media.

A total 150 were contacted to participate in the survey. The questionnaire was first shared on the Plantwise Uganda telegram group however there was very low response. After a week of very low response, the questionnaire was shared on individual Telegram inboxes with a notice to ignore if they had already participated in the survey. Seventy Plantwise Uganda telegram users were selected depending on their recent activity on the Plantwise telegram. Those that had not visited the Plantwise Uganda telegram since April 2019 were not considered.

The Eighty plant doctors were contacted using WhatsApp. A multistage sampling method was used. Using the Uganda plant doctors list, 5 clusters were created. I.e. North, South, East, West and Central regions. Plant doctors were assigned to the regions depending on their district of work. From each region, using simple random sampling 15 plant doctors were

selected. Twenty plant doctors were selected from central region because it had many districts. In case a selected individual did not have a WhatsApp account, another was selected from that same region.

The survey instrument consisted mostly of multiple choice questions and collected data on demographics, Plantwise training, Plantwise Uganda telegram membership and other social media sites.

To assess the roles and interaction of plant doctors on social media in relation to seeking or giving advice, responses were sought on the following factors; Education level, level of confidence to give advice and frequency of asking and giving advice on social media.

To improve the response, I made calls and sent reminder messages via WhatsApp and Plantwise telegram. I also used the help of a plant doctor and Plantwise Uganda telegram member in Uganda who used to remind members to participate in the survey by sending and calling members.

The survey was designed to collect the data anonymously and the responses were automatically collected by Google forms upon completion by the respondents and were exported to Microsoft excel for analysis.

Table 2. Summary of responses received for the social media and plant doctor quiz survey

Questionnaire	Number of individuals contacted		Number of responses received	Number of responses used for final data analysis		Number of responses rejected
	M	F		M	F	
Social media	102	48	67	43	20	4
Plant doctor quiz	48	22	65	37	21	7

A total of 11 submissions were rejected. 7 forms were submitted empty while 4 forms were submitted with several blank spaces.

2.2. Data analysis

The collected data was analyzed using Microsoft excel 2010 and presented as percentages and counts in form of tables and charts.

For open ended questions, the data was interpreted, and themes were created. Responses that were similar or interpreted to mean similar things were categorized under one theme (see Appendix for details).

3.0 Results

3.1. Type of actors on Plantwise Uganda telegram

3.1.1. Profile of respondents

Of the 63 respondents, males constituted 43(68%) while females constituted 20(32%). Respondents with a bachelor's degree were the highest at 37(58%), followed by those with master's degree 18(29%), and lastly those with a diploma at 8(13%) (Table 3).

Table 3. Education Level and gender of the respondents (n= 63)

Education Level	Number of respondents (%)		
	Female	Male	Row total
Masters Level	10	19	29
Bachelor's degree Level	17	41	58
Diploma Level	5	8	13
Column total (%)	32	68	100

Respondents were asked about their occupations. Figure1 below is a categorization of their responses. Agricultural Officers were the majority, represented by 38%. Civil servants and Agricultural Inspectors were respectively represented by 3%.

Figure 1. Shows the occupations of respondents on the Plantwise Uganda telegram (n= 39).

3.2. Plantwise training and access to Plantwise Uganda telegram

Table 4. Shows number of respondents trained by Plantwise who subscribe to the Plantwise Uganda telegram

Total Number of responses received	Number of respondents trained by Plantwise	Number of respondents trained by Plantwise who use the Plantwise telegram	Number of respondents trained by Plantwise who never use the Plantwise telegram
63	57	37	20

Fifty seven(90%) of all the respondents were trained by Plantwise and 65% of the respondents with Plantwise training subscribe to the Plantwise telegram while 35% never subscribe to the Plantwise telegram (Table 4).

3.3. Other social media sites where plant health actors interact on plant health issues

3.3.1. Social media sites other than Plantwise Uganda telegram that plant doctors subscribe to for plant health services.

Other than Plantwise Uganda telegram, respondents subscribe to other social media for plant health services. Over 80% percent of all the respondents use WhatsApp, just more than half of all respondents use Facebook and nearly a quarter use Instagram, Snapchat and Twitter combined (Fig.2).

Figure 2. Subscription to social media sites other than Plantwise Uganda telegram for plant health knowledge (n=63).

Fifty one percent of all the respondents subscribe to two or more social media sites, 35% of all the respondent subscribe to one social media site and 14% did not respond. Ninety one percent of the respondents with one social media site use WhatsApp and 9% of them use Facebook.

Over 70% of the respondents who have two or more social media sites use WhatsApp; Facebook combination and nearly a quarter of them use the other combinations as shown by table 5.

Table 5. Shows the multi-platform use of social media sites by respondents (n=32).

Social media use combinations by respondents	Percentage of respondents
WhatsApp; Facebook	78
WhatsApp; Instagram; Facebook; Twitter	3
WhatsApp; Instagram; Facebook; Twitter	16
Snapchat; WhatsApp; Facebook	3

All male and female participants have almost similar preferences for the use of WhatsApp and Facebook however females are likely to use Instagram compared to males (Fig.3)

Figure 3. Subscription to social media sites other than Plantwise Uganda telegram for plant health knowledge in relation gender (n=43 for Males and n= 20 for Females).

3.3.2. Frequency of use of the different social media sites

When comparing how often each of the sites are used, WhatsApp had the highest percentage response for "Often" use followed by Facebook, Telegram, Instagram and Snapchat. 43% of all respondents said they "often" use WhatsApp, 37% of all respondents "often use Facebook and 32% of all respondents said they often use Telegram (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Frequency of use of the different social media sites (n=63)

3.3.3. How often do plant doctors (non-telegram users) use social media sites to discuss plant health issues?

To establish whether plant doctors who never subscribe to Plantwise telegram ever use social media sites to discuss issues of plant health, respondents were asked how often they use social media sites to give or seek for advice on plant health.

Table 3 shows that 20(35%) of respondents with Plantwise training never subscribe to Plantwise telegram, 15% of them indicated that they have never asked for advice from social media. A half of them indicated that they have “rarely” ,a quarter have “often” and 10% have always asked for advice from social media.

Twenty percent of the 35% above who never use Plantwise telegram indicated to have “often” given advice on plant health on social media. However, half of all the non-telegram users “rarely” gave advice on social media (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. Response on the frequency of giving advice on social media site by plant doctors who never use Plantwise telegram (n= 20).

3.4. The roles and interaction of plant doctors on social media sites in relation to seeking or giving advice

3.4.1. Gender and frequency of asking for advice on the Plantwise Uganda telegram.

Of the 39 Plantwise telegram users, 95% said, they have asked for advice while 5% have never asked for advice from Plantwise Uganda telegram.

Of the 95% respondents above, 10% said they have “always”, 59% said they have “often”, and 26% said they have “rarely”, asked for advice from the Plantwise Uganda telegram.

Sixty eight percent of the male respondents compared to 36% of the females who use Plantwise telegram said they have “ often” asked for advice from the Plantwise Uganda telegram (Fig.6).

Figure 6. Frequency of asking for advice by plant doctors on the Plantwise Uganda telegram in relation to gender (n= 28 Males & n= 11 Females).

3.4.2. Gender and frequency of giving advice on the Plantwise Uganda telegram.

Ninety seven percent of the respondents who are Plantwise telegram users, said they have given advice on the telegram and 3% of them have never given advice on the Plantwise telegram.

Of the 97% respondents, 18% said they have “always”,51% have “often” and 28% have “rarely”, given advice on the Plantwise telegram.

Forty six percent of the 28 male respondents who are Telegram users compared to 64% of 11 females (Telegram users) said they have “often” given advice on the Plantwise Uganda telegram (Fig. 7).

Figure 7. Frequency of giving advice by plant doctors on the Plantwise Uganda telegram in relation to gender (n=28 males & n= 11 females).

3.4.3. Gender and level of confidence to give advice on the Plantwise Uganda telegram by plant doctors.

Nearly a quarter of Plantwise telegram users (21%), said they are “highly confident”,67% are “very confident” and 12% are slightly confident to give advice on the Plantwise Uganda telegram.

Over 80% of the women compared to 61% of the men who use Plantwise telegram said are “ very confident” to give advice on the Telegram (Fig.8).

Figure 8. Level of confidence to give advice on the Plantwise Uganda telegram in relation to gender (n=28 for Males & n= 11 for Females).

3.4.4. Education level and frequency of asking for advice on the Plantwise Uganda telegram. Results show that of the 39 respondents who use the Plantwise Uganda telegram, 10% said they have "always", 59% have "often", 26% have "rarely", asked for advice on the Plantwise Uganda telegram. 5% said they have never asked for advice on the Plantwise Uganda telegram.

Fifty eight percent of the respondents possessing a master's degree, 59% of the respondents possessing a bachelor's degree and 60% of the respondents possessing a diploma said they have "often", asked for advice on the Plantwise Uganda telegram (Fig.9).

Figure 9. Frequency of asking for advice by plant doctors on the Plantwise Uganda telegram in relation to education level. (n= 12 Masters level, n=22 Bachelors level & n= 5 Diploma level).

3.4.5. Education level and frequency of giving advice on the Plantwise Uganda telegram

A half of the respondents with a master's degree (50%), more than half with a bachelor's degree (55%) and nearly half of the respondents with a diploma (40%) indicated that they have "often" given advice on the Plantwise telegram. More than half (60%) of the respondents with a diploma said they have rarely given advice on the Plantwise telegram while 5% with a bachelor's degree said they have never given advice on the Plantwise telegram (Fig.10).

Figure 10. Frequency of giving advice by plant doctors on the Plantwise Uganda telegram in relation to education level. (n= 12 Masters level, n=22 Bachelors level & n= 5 Diploma level).

3.4.6. Education and Level of confidence to give advice on the Plantwise telegram

Of the 39 respondents on the Plantwise telegram, more than a half (67%) said were Very confident, nearly a quarter (21%) said were highly confident and 13% were slightly confident to give advice on the Plantwise telegram

Over 70% of the respondents with master's degree and more than half with a bachelor's degree indicated that they are very confident to give advice on Plantwise telegram. Nearly a half of the respondents with a diploma indicated that they are very confident to give advice the Plantwise telegram (Fig.11).

Figure 11. Level of confidence to give advice by plant doctors on the Plantwise Uganda telegram in relation to education level. (n= 12 Masters level, n=22 Bachelors level & n= 5 Diploma level).

3.4.7. Plantwise training and level of confidence to give advice on Plantwise Uganda telegram by plant doctors.

Of the 39 respondents on the Plantwise telegram, 95% were trained by Plantwise while 5% had no Plantwise training and more than half indicated they were very confident (67%), nearly a quarter said were highly confident (21%) and 13% of them said they were slightly confident to give advice on the Plantwise telegram.

Respondents without Plantwise training were as confident to give advice on social media as those who with Plantwise training as indicated by figure 12 which shows that 68% of respondents with Plantwise training said were very confident to give advice on the Plantwise telegram, 50% of the respondents without Plantwise training also indicated that they were very confident to give advice on the Plantwise telegram.

Figure 12. Level of confidence to give advice on Plantwise Uganda telegram or other social media platform in relation to Plantwise training. (n=37 With Plantwise training & n= 2 Without Plantwise training).

3.4.8. Level of confidence to give advice on Plantwise Uganda telegram in relation to education Level and Plantwise training.

All the 39 respondents who use Plantwise telegram stated that they were confident to give advice and 37 of them were trained while 2 were not trained by Plantwise.

Of the 37 respondents, 24% with a master's degree, 38% with a bachelor's degree and 5% with a diploma said were very confident to give advice on the Plantwise telegram. A half of the respondents minus Plantwise training with a diploma said were highly confident while the other half with a bachelor's degree said was very confident to give advice on the Plantwise telegram. (Fig.13).

Figure 13. Level of confidence to give advice on the Plantwise Uganda telegram in relation to education level and Plantwise training (n=37 With Plantwise training & n= 2 Without Plantwise training).

3.4.9. The interaction between those who give advice and those that ask for advice on plant health from social media.

Ninety two percent of all the respondents said they have given advice on the social media sites while 91% of all the respondents said they have ever sought assistance from the different social media sites.

3.5. The role of plant doctor quiz in the sharing and transfer of plant health knowledge.

3.5.1. Profile of respondents

Of the 70 plant doctors who were contacted, 65 responded yielding a response rate of 93% however 58 responses were used for the final survey. 7 responses were rejected because they were incompletely filled. Of the 58 responses, 37 were males and 21 were females.

All the 58 respondents were trained by Plantwise and 44(76%) had done a quiz while 14(24%) had never done a quiz. In the 76% respondents who use the quiz, males constituted 70% while females made 30%.

3.5.2. Factors that influence the accessibility of plant doctor quizzes to the different plant doctors.

To address this objective, plant doctors provided their responses to the following parameters; value of the plant doctor quiz as a learning tool for plant doctors, whether the frequency and number of questions of the quiz influenced the response to the quiz, the effectiveness of the communication channels via which the quiz is shared and whether indicating names on the quiz influenced response to the quiz.

3.5.3. Communication channels; How plant doctors like to receive the plant doctor quiz.

In this case, respondents could give multiple responses on the channels through which they would like to hear about the plant doctor quiz. Most plant doctors who are quiz users would like to hear about the quiz via emails at 73%.(Fig 14).

Figure 14. Response on the different communication channels through which plant doctors like to hear about the quiz (n=44).

3.5.4. Response on how frequent plant doctors like to receive the plant doctor quiz and the number of quiz questions.

Fourteen (32%) of the 44 respondents would like to receive the quiz monthly, 13(30%) would like to receive the quiz weekly and 8(18%) of them would like to do the quiz bi-weekly (Table 6).

Table 6. Response by plant doctors on how frequent they like to receive a plant doctor quiz (n= 44).

When to receive a plant doctor quiz	(%) of plant doctor quiz users
Whenever I can	2
Everyday	2
Twice a week	18
Once a week	30
Every after two weeks	9
Monthly	32
Once every 3 months	5
No response	2
Total (%)	100

On whether to make the quiz longer (more than 10 questions), 24 (55%) of all the 44 respondents said no while 20(45%) said yes to increase the number of questions.

Of the 20 respondents who would like a quiz with more questions, 40% would like to receive the quiz biweekly and 35% monthly (Fig.15).

Figure 15. Response on the how frequent plant doctors like to receive the quiz and the number of quiz questions (n=20).

3.5.5. Response on whether plant doctor doctors put names on the quizzes and how comfortable they feel about sharing their names on the plant doctor quizzes.

Four (9%) of the quiz users were uncomfortable with sharing their names on the plant doctor quiz however, 12(27%) of them were “extremely comfortable”,21(48%) were “very comfortable” and 6 (14%) were “fairly comfortable”, to share names on the plant doctor quiz. 1 (2%) did not respond.

Thirty three (75%) of the respondents who do the quiz said yes while 11(25%) of them said no when they were asked if they had put their names on the quiz. Interestingly, only 2(18%) of the respondents who never put names on the quiz said were uncomfortable with putting names on the quiz while 9(82%) were either extremely comfortable, very comfortable or fairly comfortable with having their names on the quiz. Indeed 45% of them said were very comfortable. (Fig 16).

Figure 16. Response on whether plant doctors had put names on the quiz they answered and how comfortable they feel about having their names on the quizzes. (n=33 for Put names on the quiz & n= 11 for Did not put names on the quiz).

3.5.6. Perception of respondents on the value of plant doctor quiz as a learning tool for plant doctors.

All the respondents who do the quiz indicated that the plant doctor quiz is either good or excellent as a learning tool for plant doctors.

Table 1. Shows the perception of quiz users on plant doctors quiz as a learning tool for plant doctors (n=44).

Statements	strongly agree (%)	Agree (%)	No opinion (%)	Disagree (%)	strongly disagree (%)
The contents of the plant doctor quiz are interesting and enjoyable to do.	57	25	2	5	11
Plant doctor quiz provide new knowledge	45	36	2	5	11
The contents of the plant doctor quiz increase the diagnostic knowledge & skills	57	25	4	5	9
Knowledge from the plant doctor quiz can be used to solve pest & disease problems	52	32	2	2	11

3.5.7. The different ways quiz users encourage other plant doctors to participate in the plant doctor quiz.

Eighty percent of the respondents who are quiz users stated that they have encouraged other plant doctors to answer a plant doctor quiz. This is mostly done by word of mouth and just under half had forwarded the link to colleagues (Fig. 17).

Figure 17. The different ways how plant doctors encourage others to do the plant doctor quiz (n=44).

3.5.8. Factor that lead to a plant doctor to start a quiz but fail to complete answering it.

Records from CABI of Ugandan quiz users show that out of 89 quizzes that plant doctors started, 60 (67%) were answered completely while 29 (33%) were partially completed. The data collected as part of this study show that a quarter of the 44 respondents started answering a quiz and failed to complete it.

Nearly half of the respondents did not complete the quizzes due to work related reason (45%), and approximately a third for technical reasons (27% internet access and 9% phone battery). 18% did not indicate why they failed to complete the quizzes (Fig.18).

Figure 18. Reasons given by plant doctors for partial completing of quizzes (n=11).

3.5.9. Factors that prevented the plant doctors from answering the quizzes

More than a half of the 44 respondents reported having missed doing a quiz (61%) and 30% of them missed due work-related reasons (30%), more half missed due to technical reasons (30% being off the telegram, 22% internet access & 7% phone battery). 18% did not disclose reasons why they missed doing the quiz (Fig.19 & Appendix 4 for details).

Figure 19. Reasons that prevented plant doctors from answering plant doctor quizzes (n=27).

4.0 Discussions

4.1. Types of actors on the Plantwise Uganda telegram.

Plantwise Uganda telegram membership is composed of many Extension Officers who are plant doctors, Agricultural inspectors, Heads of department at the district level, specialists from the academia and other non-technical members like the project managers who are important actors in plant health.

All Plantwise telegram respondents had a minimum of a diploma and a maximum of a master's degree with majority of them being Agricultural Officers who are actively involved in the day to day running of plant clinics at the different local governments. The composition and qualification of members on the Plantwise Uganda telegram brings together a diversity of individuals and institutions who are experts in plant diseases diagnosis which places members in a position to provide advice with authority on plant health related issues. Mugambi and Oronje (2016) further notes that the diversity in members on the Telegram networks improve surveillance at local and regional levels.

4.2. Status of access to Plantwise telegram in relation Plantwise training

Although most of respondents are trained by Plantwise, over 30% of them do not use the Plantwise Uganda telegram which highlights a gap in awareness of the Telegram group. In a study done by Byomire et al (2016) found that over 80% of Ugandan Urban Agriculturalist lacked awareness of the use of social media in agriculture and Fuess (2011) reports that lack of capacity in using social media, nonexistent or poor internet connectivity and poor electricity supply limits the use of social media in agricultural extension services. Plant doctors and other plant health actors who are non-telegram members need awareness of the Telegram existence, its use and services and potential benefits in being a member of the group. This can be achieved through awareness programs/campaigns, training programs and workshops to help plant doctors and other plant health actors understand and use the social media better (Suchiradipta and Saravanan 2015; Thomas and Laseinde 2015). Equally important was put forward by Barau and Afrad (2017) where they recommended enhancement of infrastructures that support proper utilization of social media like internet access, and electricity supply.

4.3. Other social media sites plant doctors subscribe to for plant health services.

WhatsApp, Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and Snapchat were other social media sites were plant doctors access plant health information. WhatsApp was the most frequently used platform followed by Facebook and Telegram came third. This implies that people are more likely to visit WhatsApp and Facebook compared to Telegram for plant health services. Although Telegram is the preferred media for use by Plantwise, it is less popular among plant doctors in Uganda (Plantwise Annual report 2018). According to the Uganda National Information Technology survey (2018), majority (92.9%) of households who use social media

subscribe to Facebook followed by 55.1% who subscribe to WhatsApp. It is therefore likely that most of their contacts subscribe to Facebook and WhatsApp compared to Telegram.

Multi -platform use is high at over 50%. Majority of Plant doctors and other Extension officers have two or more social media sites. WhatsApp; Facebook was the most popular combination to the agreement with the study done by Byomire *et al.*, (2016) which implies that it is likely to have plant doctors on any of these social media sites. Although women seemed to like WhatsApp more compared to men, the difference was small (4%) this was a similar situation with men and Facebook use where there was a difference of 1% between men and women who indicated to use Facebook.

When they were asked how often they have given advice on social media in relation to plant health, plant doctors who never subscribe to Plantwise Uganda telegram but use other social media sites, 80% positively responded. This indicates that plant doctors use the other social media sites to discuss issues pertaining to plant health services and the study points to the fact that plant doctors will most likely discuss plant health matters on those sites where they spend most of their time. It is important therefore that discussions on these other social media sites that relate to plant health are captured to ensure quality and streamlining of information flow.

4.4. The role and interaction of plant doctors on social media sites in relation to giving and asking for advice on plant health.

Plantwise Uganda telegram facilitates quick sharing of queries on pest outbreaks, spread and sharing of management options among members who in turn disseminate to farmers and extension staffs. In this process, there is an observed trend of those who post queries (questioners) and those who provide answers to the posted queries (Advice givers). It is therefore important to assess the actors (advice seekers and advice givers) interactions and relationships on Plantwise Uganda telegram and other social media sites in relation to seeking or giving advice about plant health.

4.4.1. Frequency of giving and asking for advice on social media by plant doctors.

Results show that members use Plantwise Uganda telegram and other social media sites to seek and give advice on plant health with members on Plantwise Uganda telegram being more active. This could be the case because Plantwise Uganda telegram offers an organised platform for subscribers to give and seek assistance on exclusively plant health related matters. Plantwise Uganda telegram is composed of plant health experts from national Universities and CABI, who usually provide diagnostic services for cases that prove hard to handle by plant doctors. Plantwise telegram offers a quick alternative to solving difficult plant health problems to the plant doctors who have no link with the national diagnostics centers. According to Danielsen *et al* (2012), plant doctors in Uganda rarely send samples to diagnostic

centers because of weak linkages between the plant clinics and the local diagnostic institutions. Plantwise telegram offers the plant doctors an opportunity to seek for quick assistance via electronic enquires which they otherwise would not have managed with the local diagnostics laboratories (Miller et al 2009; Mugambi and Oronje 2016).

Over a quarter of the respondents rarely ask or give advice on the Plantwise Uganda telegram (26% and 28% respectively). Barau and Afrad (2017) acknowledges that most social media which are agriculture related are challenged by a having a large number of members who are passive with a few who are active which limits knowledge sharing and information flow. It therefore important that consideration is given to find ways that would encourage participation of more members.

Although there are other social media sites like WhatsApp and Facebook that this study was able to establish that respondents use for seeking and giving advice on plant health services, it was not possible to ascertain from the results how much issues of plant health services are prioritised on such sites like it is with the Plantwise Uganda telegram.

4.4.2. Frequency of giving advice on the Plantwise Uganda telegram in relation to education level and gender.

The results reveal that plant doctors with masters and bachelor's degree education are more likely to give advice compared to those with a diploma because they are more confident. This is supported by results that show respondents with a diploma having the highest (40% compared to 9% bachelor's degree & 8% master's degree) proportion of respondents who indicated being slightly confident to give advice on the telegram. Furthermore 60% (more than half) of diploma holders indicated having rarely given advice, this by proportion exceed by almost triple that of masters and bachelor's degree holders who indicated that have rarely given advice on the telegram (25% for masters & 23% for bachelor's degree holders). This implies that education has influence the level of confidence hence the frequency to give advice on plant health issues on the Plantwise Uganda telegram.

Results further reveal that females' respondents are more likely to give advice than males. This was because women felt very confident to give advice on the Plantwise Uganda telegram than men. These results are supported by studies done by (Young and McSporran 2001; Duggan and Brenner 2013) that found women to be more motivated, communicated better and were more self-disciplined online compared to males who often require more external supervision and control however these results are in disagreement with Rollero and Tartaglia (2019) who found men more likely to communicate and express their opinions than women on social media sites.

4.4.3. Frequency of giving advice on the Plantwise Uganda telegram in relation to education level and Plantwise training

Education and Plantwise training have a positive influence on how frequent plant doctors give advice on the Plantwise Uganda telegram. Results depicts that members on the Plantwise telegram without Plantwise training with tertiary education are as likely to provide advice on the platform as those with Plantwise training and tertiary education. It is observed that education level influenced to a greater extent the level confidence to give advice on the Plantwise Uganda telegram. However, level of education had no influence on how often, plant doctors asked for advice from the Plantwise Uganda telegram.

These findings highlight the importance of having technical expertise on social media groups to ably support discussions in the different fields. The results reveal that members on the Plantwise Uganda telegram are willing to share their knowledge at their different academic levels which ensures quality of advice and continuous learning for the junior participants.

4.4.4 The interaction between those who give advice and those that seek for advice on the social media.

There is a very small difference between the advice givers and those who post queries seeking for help on social media. Members almost equally participate in both roles on the social media site studied. Results show a 1% difference between those who have given and those who have asked for advice from the Plantwise Uganda telegram.

4.5. Factors that influence the accessibility of plant doctor quizzes to plant doctors.

4.5.1. Value of plant doctor quiz as a learning tool for plant doctors.

The main aim of the plant doctor quiz is to test and increase the plant doctor's diagnostic knowledge and skills. It has been widely reported, (Lahijani & Kateb (2004); Khurshid & Ansari (2012); Goud & Begum (2014)), that quizzes are highly effective lifelong learning tools that motivate students to learn and assess the level of knowledge related to specific content and test the analytical and critical thinking ability of students on selected topics. Rao and Dicarlo (2000), said that quizzes have a positive influence on knowledge retention.

Feedback from the study on using plant doctor quiz as a learning tool for sharing of knowledge on plant health was positive and encouraging. Most plant doctors overall ranked the plant doctor quiz as an important learning tool for plant doctors and majority agreed that; the contents of the plant doctor quizzes are interesting and enjoyable to do, provide new knowledge, and that the contents increase their diagnostic knowledge & skills and that knowledge from the plant doctor quiz can be directly used to solve pest & disease problems.

Overall these results indicate that the plant doctor who take the quizzes believe them to be an important tool to improve their plant health knowledge and diagnostic skills.

4.5.2. Frequency of receiving the plant doctor quiz and the number of questions.

Generally, plant doctors are comfortable with doing the quiz once every month and the quiz having 10 questions. Members who suggested to have the quiz more than once a month would only do this when the number of questions is maintained. Therefore, keeping the status as it is now with regards to the frequency of the doing the plant doctor quiz and the question number is supported.

4.5.3. Effectiveness of the communication channels through which plant doctors receive the plant doctor quiz.

Currently Plantwise Uganda telegram is the main channel through which plant doctors can receive the plant doctor quiz. A quiz link is normally shared on Plantwise Uganda platform inviting members to answer the quiz. Depending on the Plantwise Uganda telegram as the main channel to share the quiz, can be a challenge in instances where members temporarily go off the Plantwise Uganda telegram for several reasons like changing the registered line or changing the device.

The study shows that majority of the plant doctors would like to receive the quiz via their emails and WhatsApp inboxes. The personal attachment that comes with receiving a message in the inbox could be the reason driving the result. Sharing the quiz on the Plantwise Uganda telegram seems like a general communication. Therefore, sharing the quiz via the plant doctors' inboxes can go a long way in improving accessibility of the plant doctor quiz.

Plant doctors have disseminated information about the quiz between themselves to a limited extent, first by directly talking to other plant doctors privately and at meetings and forwarding the quiz link to their colleagues. For maximum reach of the quiz, it is important that deliberate efforts are instituted to improve the accessibility of the plant doctor quiz to the plant doctors.

4.5.4. How plant doctors feel about sharing their names on the plant doctor quiz.

Plant doctors were generally comfortable with sharing their names on the plant doctor quiz and a large percentage had shared names on the quiz however amongst those who said they were comfortable with sharing their names on the quiz, over eighty percent did not put names on the quiz. This could have been so because the option for including names, was optional.

Generally doing a quiz, comes with a feeling of being assessed, may be some plant doctors feel this way hence the failure to include names on the quiz. This may indicate a lack of confidence about the taking of the quiz, if someone was confident that they were going to do well they may be more inclined to include their names whereas those lacking may defer. It is however important to note that plant doctors may use any identity they are comfortable with and make sure that this same identity is always used when answering the proceeding quizzes for proper records.

Six percent of the respondents said had put a name on the quiz yet were not comfortable with doing so. This may be through a sense of duty and being obedient or it could reflect the latest quizzes where it is mandatory to fill in a name.

4.6. Reasons for partial completion of the plant doctor quizzes.

According to the National Information Technology survey report (2018), Wakabi & Gronlund (2019) indicated that high access cost of internet, slow connection and lack of network connection limit internet use in Uganda. The social media tax that was introduced in 2018 of UGX 200(USD 0.05) per day further complicates the situation (Mayambala & Rukundo 2018).

The impact of these constraints is reflected in the study findings as it is observed that most plant doctors answer the plant doctor quiz while at work where they can access free internet services. However, this results in them getting engaged with other duties and fail to finish the quiz.

Loss of network connection while answering the quiz is another reason that over a quarter plant doctors gave as a reason for not finishing a quiz. It is important to note that most plant doctors work in rural areas where such challenges as highlighted in the Uganda National Information Technology survey are very common. Internet penetration is still very low which stands at 14% according to (Gillwald and Tsubira 2019).

4.7. Reasons that prevented plant doctors from answering plant doctor quizzes.

More than half of plant doctors have ever missed doing plant doctor quiz due technical reasons. These reasons relate to plant doctor's failure to receive the quiz when they change their devices or the registered contacts on the telegram, this situation is aggravated by their taking long to check their emails where the quiz link is also shared.

Phone battery and related problems is another reason that plant doctors gave for missing quizzes. According to the UBOS (2016), only 20% percent of households in Uganda have access to electricity and majority of people minus electricity live in the rural areas. Plant doctors who work in villages with no electricity, tend to limit use of their mobile phones to save on the battery life.

Sharing the quiz using multiple avenues especially on WhatsApp could reduce the number of plant doctors who miss the quiz. WhatsApp has a big user base amongst social media users in Uganda therefore a plant doctor who has gone off telegram for some reason will most likely prioritize installing WhatsApp to access his/her contacts. CABI through the country coordinators and quiz users can seek membership to the different WhatsApp groups where plant doctors interact to share the quiz link directly to those groups.

Although the plant doctor quiz received a positive response as a learning tool for plant doctors from this study, a quarter of the plant doctors missed the quiz yet they had the capacity to

take the quiz but chose not to because they were busy, this reveals lurking reasons that could relate to priority and interest of plant doctors to participate in the quiz. It is therefore important to establish the incentives that may influence plant doctors' interest to take the quiz to maximize the plant doctor quiz uptake. It should be noted that plant doctors' who miss doing the quiz for some reason, they have the opportunity of finding the quizzes online and can be accessed anytime with no restrictions. Therefore, a plant doctor who misses doing a quiz because of poor network in one place, has a chance of accessing the quiz online in places with better internet connectivity.

4.8. Limitation to the study.

It is important to note that the results of this study have to be understood in the context that responses to some questions may have more to do with the way respondents interpreted the questions. Responses like "always" were open to the respondent's interpretations. This was a weak point to the data collection for Always in this case meant every day. There was over representation of male respondents because the ratio of female to male plant doctors is high in Uganda.

The low number of responses for some categories was a challenge during analysis for example there was a category that had only 2 respondents this could have been brought about by the limited time to collect the data which affected the number of respondents.

Since was done online and responses were anonymous, it was impossible to make follow ups in cases where responses required elaboration.

Many members on the Plantwise Uganda telegram were not active, they last visited the platform in March, and some take almost a month minus visiting their Plantwise Uganda telegram accounts. This was a problem as most members failed to respond to the questionnaires which affected the response rate. The email addresses of some quiz users were invalid.

Important assumption made was that respondents in the survey understood and interpreted the questions as per the survey objectives and that all the responses they gave related to the actual behaviors of the individual respondents in the field.

5.0 Conclusion

It is important to realize that social media like WhatsApp, Facebook and Twitter have come to stay, and are becoming part of everyday life amongst people of all levels (Koseoglu Tuncer 2016). The use of social media compliments and improves the Agricultural extension and advisory services in many ways as it plays important role in enhancing interactions and information flows among the different plant health actors (Byamira *et al.*, 2016).

Plantwise Uganda telegram is composed of members ranging from field extension officers, academia and diagnostic specialists and majority of the members have tertiary education and trained by Plantwise enabling them to provide the required services in plant health.

There is a gap in awareness about the Plantwise Uganda telegram amongst plant doctors making popularizing the Plantwise telegram a priority in order to bring on board other plant doctors who are non-members.

In addition to Plantwise telegram, plant doctors mostly use WhatsApp and Facebook for plant health interactions with WhatsApp being the most popular social media site. Multi-platform use is high with WhatsApp; Facebook being the popular use combination

it is on such sites where they spent most of their time that they are more likely to discuss plant health issues, it is important therefore that ways are found through which such social media sites can be utilized to support plant health knowledge sharing and transfer.

However, this study fell short of establishing the details of the discussions on other social media sites other than Plantwise telegram in terms of how much they relate to plant health services, this may be probed further.

Education level, Plantwise training, Time of stay on the Plantwise telegram and gender were important factors that influenced giving of advice on the telegram. Education level greatly influenced the level of confidence to give advice on the Plantwise telegram. However, education level did not influence how much plant doctors sought for advice from the Plantwise telegram.

Having active women on a social media site might have advantages in terms of knowledge and information sharing. Women were observed to be good online communicators with a good sense of self-discipline and commitment to share knowledge online. A greater proportion of women indicated having participated in giving advice compared to the men. Men participated most as questioners on the telegram.

Plant doctor quiz is an important tool for plant doctors to test their diagnostic skills and acquire knowledge. Use other communication channels like emails and WhatsApp accounts to share the plant doctor quiz to improve accessibility.

Keeping the plant doctor quiz at a monthly schedule with the current number of questions (10 questions) was widely supported by respondents in the study.

High access cost of internet, poor network connectivity and complete absence of internet connection in some parts of the country are reasons for that prevent plant doctor from doing and partially filling the quizzes they start. Other plant doctors with the capacity to take the quiz miss taking quizzes, because they are engaged with their duties, so they choose not to take the quiz.

Popularizing the Plantwise Uganda telegram and plant doctor quiz should be prioritised by plant health actors if they are to be maximumly utilized to actualize the important goal of supporting provision of knowledge on plant health services. This can be done through social media literacy training programs and workshops to help plant doctors and other plant health actors understand and use the social media and plant doctor quizzes better. Interventions that support the reduction of internet accessibility costs and those that improve internet connectivity should be prioritised by the Ugandan government and development partners. Subsidized internet access rates is recommended as a possible short term solution to high access internet costs.

References

- Anyanwu, E.U., Ossai-Onah, V.O., & Iroeze, P.C. (2013). Use of social media tools among Nigerian undergraduates in three selected tertiary institutions in Imo State, Nigeria
- Barau AA, Afrad SI. (2017). An overview of social media use in agricultural extension service delivery.8(3):50-61. doi:10.17700/jai.2017.8.3.395
- Baruah, T. D. (2012). Effectiveness of Social Media as a tool of communication and its potential for technology enabled connections: A micro-level study. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 2(5), 1-10.
- Brace, I. (2018). *Questionnaire design: How to plan, structure and write survey material for effective market research*. Kogan Page Publishers.
- Byomire G, Namisango F, Kafuko M. (2016). Use of Social Media to Strengthen Service Delivery for Urban Agriculture in Uganda. doi:10.1109/ISTAFRICA.2016.7530594
- Center for Agriculture and Biosciences International (CABI). *Plantwise Annual Report 2018* <http://www.Plantwise.org/wp-content/uploads/sites/4/2019/04/Plantwise-Annual-Report-2018.pdf>. Accessed October 2019
- Center for Agriculture and Biosciences International (CABI). *Plantwise Annual Report 2017*. <http://www.Plantwise.org/wp-content/uploads/sites/4/2019/03/Plantwise-Annual-Report-2017.pdf>. Accessed October 2019
- Constantinides, E., & Fountain, S. J. (2008). Web 2.0: Conceptual foundations and marketing issues. *Journal of direct, data and digital marketing practice*, 9(3), 231-244.
- Constantinides, E. (2014). Foundations of social media marketing. *Procedia-Social and behavioural sciences*, 148, 40-57.
- Danielsen, S., & Matsiko, F. B. (2016). Using a plant health system framework to assess plant clinic performance in Uganda. *Food Security*, 8(2), 345-359
- Dicarlo SE. Peer instruction improves Performance on quizzes. 2014;(April). doi:10.1152/advances.2000.24.1.51
- Duggan, M., & Brenner, J. (2013). *The demographics of social media users, 2012* (Vol. 14). Washington, DC: Pew Research Center's Internet & American Life Project.
- Fuess, L. C. (2011). An analysis and recommendations of the use of social media within the Cooperative Extension System: opportunities, risks, and barriers.
- Gillwald, A., Mothobi, O., Ndiwalana, A., & Tusubira, F. F. (2019). *The State of ICT in Uganda*. <https://www.africaportal.org/publications/state-ict-uganda/>. Accessed in October 2019.

- Goud, B. M., & Begum, G. S. (2014). Integrated quiz competition: a innovative method of teaching and learning in undergraduate first year medical course at RAKMHSU, UAE. *British Journal of Medicine and Medical Research*, 4(20), 3755-3766.
- Kakungulu-Mayambala, R., & Rukundo, S. (2018). Implications of Uganda's New Social Media Tax. *East African Journal of Peace & Human Rights*, 24, 2.
- Kamp, M., Messerschmidt, M., & Rugambwa, I. (2016). The impact of social media on the run-up to the 2016 elections in Uganda. *Assessing the impact of social media on political communication and civic engagement in Uganda*, 21-30.
- Kaplan, A. M., & Haenlein, M. (2010). Users of the world, unite! The challenges and opportunities of Social Media. *Business horizons*, 53(1), 59-68.
- Kim K, Yoo-Lee E, Sin SJ (2011) Social media as information source: Undergraduates' use and evaluation behavior. *Proc Am Soc Inf Sci Technol*. 2011;48(1):1-3. doi:10.1002/meet.14504801283
- Koçak, N. G., & Oyman, M. (2012). Social media usage behaviours of individuals: An application in Eskişehir. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 3(22), 177-188
- Köseoğlu Ö, Tuncer A.(2016). Designing Social Media Policy for Local Governments: Opportunities and Challenges. In: *Public Administration and Information Technology*. 23-36. doi:10.1007/978-3-319-17722-9_2
- Khurshid, F., & Ansari, U. (2012). Effects of innovative teaching strategies on students' performance. *Global Journal of Human Social Science Linguistics & Education*, 12(10), 46-53.
- Lahijani S KR. (2004). The effect of PBL quizzes and lecture based method on short term performance of dentistry students. *J Med Educ*.2:77-80.
- Mayfield, A. (2008). What is social media. http://indianstrategicknowledgeonline.com/web/mayfield_strat_for_soc_media.pdf. Accessed August 2019.
- Miller, S. A., Beed, F. D., & Harmon, C. L. (2009). Plant disease diagnostic capabilities and networks. *Annual review of phytopathology*, 47, 15-38.
- Mugambi, I., Williams, F., Muthomi, J., Chege, F., & Oronje, M. (2016). Diagnostic support to Plantwise plant doctors in Kenya. *Journal of Agricultural Extension and Rural Development*, 8(11), 232-239.
- National Information and Technology Authority Uganda,(2013). Government of Uganda social

- media guide.(July).<https://www.nita.go.ug/sites/default/files/publications/Government-of-Uganda-Social-Media-Guide.pdf>. Accessed on 7th/October 2019.
- Osterrieder, A. (2013). The value and use of social media as communication tool in the plant sciences. *Plant methods*, 9(1), 26.
- Rao, S. P., & DiCarlo, S. E. (2000). Peer instruction improves performance on quizzes. *Advances in physiology education*, 24(1), 51-55.
- Rollero, C., Daniele, A., & Tartaglia, S. (2019). Do men post and women view? The role of gender, personality and emotions in online social activity. *Cyberpsychology*, 13(1).
- Saravanan, R., Suchiradipta, B., Chowdhury, A., Hall, K., & Odame, H. H. (2015). Social media for rural advisory services. *What Works in Rural Advisory Services?* 111.
- Siniscalco, M. T., & Auriat, N. (2005). Questionnaire design. *Quantitative research methods in educational planning*, 8.
- Thakur, M., Pandit, V., Rehman, A., Cameron, K. H., & Beverley, C. (2018). Leveraging Information and Communication Technologies for Strengthening Plant Health Extension Services in South Asia. *Extncn2018: Transforming agricultural extension systems*.
- The Collaboration on International ICT Policy for East and Southern Africa (CIPESA), (2018). National Information Technology Survey 2017/2018 Report. <https://www.nita.go.ug/sites/default/files/publications/National%20IT%20Survey%20April%2010th.pdf>. Accessed in October 2019
- Thomas, K. A., & Laseinde, A. A. (2015). Training Needs Assessment on the Use of Social Media among Extension Agents in Oyo State, Nigeria. *Agrárinformatika/Journal of Agricultural Informatics*, 6(1), 110-111.
- Vázquez-García, M. (2018). Collaborative-group testing improves learning and knowledge retention of human physiology topics in second-year medical students. *Advances in physiology education*, 42(2), 232-239.
- Wright HJ, Ochilo W, Pearson A, et al. (2016). Using ICT to Strengthen Agricultural Extension Systems for Plant Health Using ICT to Strengthen Agricultural Extension Systems for Plant Health.6505(February). doi:10.1080/10496505.2015.1120214
- Yeboah, J., & Ewur, G. D. (2014). The impact of WhatsApp messenger usage on student's performance in Tertiary Institutions in Ghana. *Journal of Education and practice*, 5(6), 157-164.
- Young S, Mcsporrán M. (2001). Confident men-Successful women: Gender differences in online learning. *Proc EdMedia 2001 Conf*. 1.

Wakabi, W. (2017). When Citizens in Authoritarian States Use Facebook for Social Ties but Not Political Participation. In *Politics, Protest, and Empowerment in Digital Spaces* (pp. 192-214). IGI Global.

Uganda Bureau of Statistics, (2016). *The National Population and Housing Census 2014-Main Report*, Kampala Uganda.

Appendices

Appendix 1 - Questionnaire on Social media and Plant health

My name is Zacchaeus Mukasa Nsubuga, Agricultural officer and Plant doctor working with Kayunga district local government. I am currently a student of Master of advanced studies in integrated crop management (MAS -ICM) at the university of Neuchâtel, Switzerland supported by CABI. I am writing a thesis on the role of plant doctor quizzes and social media (Plantwise Uganda telegram) in plant health knowledge sharing and transfer in Uganda. I request for your treasured time to fill some questions. The study will provide facts for improvement of digital plant health services. Your responses will remain anonymous. I will hold the data confidential and only for academic purposes. If you have any questions about the survey, please email me: zackzenith@yahoo.com or whatsApp +256776261998

1. Gender

Mark only one oval.

- Male
- Female

2. District

3. Occupation

4. Education Level

Mark only one oval.

- Doctorate Level
- Masters Level
- Bachelor's degree Level
- Diploma Level
- High school Level
- Other:

5. Have you been trained by Plantwise?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

6. Do you subscribe to Plantwise Uganda telegram?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (please proceed to question 7)
- No (Please go to question 8)

7. How long have you been on Plantwise Uganda telegram?

Mark only one oval.

- Less than a year
- One year
- Two years
- Three years

8. Other than Plantwise Uganda telegram, what other social media groups/applications do you subscribe to for plant health issues? (please select all that apply, can be more than one)

Check all that apply.

- Snapchat
- WhatsApp
- Instagram
- Facebook
- Other:

9. How often do you use the following social media sites? (select all that apply, can be more than one)

Mark only one oval per row.

	(0) Never	(1) Rarely	(2) Often times	(3) Always
Snapchat				
WhatsApp				
Instagram				
Facebook				
telegram				

10. How often have you given recommendations on Plantwise Uganda telegram or other social media?

Mark only one oval.

- Always
- Often times
- Rarely
- Never

11. How confident are you to give recommendations on the Plantwise Uganda telegram or other social media?

Mark only one oval.

- Highly confident
- Very confident
- Slightly confident
- Not confident

12. How often have you asked for assistance/recommendation(s) on Plantwise Uganda telegram or other social media?

Mark only one oval.

- Always
- Often times
- Rarely
- Never

13. Have you directly used information from Plantwise Uganda telegram or other social media?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

14. How much do you agree with the following statements?

Mark only one oval per row.

statements	(0) Not applicable/No Opinion	(1) strongly disagree	(2) disagree	(3) agree	(4) strongly agree
The use of Social media in a plant health system will significantly improve the diagnosis and recommendations given to farmers.					
The use of Plantwise Uganda telegram and other social media increases accessibility to plant health information					

The use of Plantwise Uganda telegram and other social media in plant health system provide information for early detection of new crop pests and diseases in the country.					
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15. What stops you from using Plantwise Uganda telegram as often as possible? (please respond if you subscribe to Plantwise Uganda telegram)

16. Concerning the subject of the survey, suggest ways how to improve the use of Plantwise Uganda telegram or other social media in plant health.

17. Have you ever heard of plant doctor quizzes?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

18. Have you ever done a plant doctor Quiz?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

Appendix 2- Questionnaire for Plant doctor Quiz

My name is Zacchaeus Mukasa Nsubuga, Agricultural officer and Plant doctor working with Kayunga district local government. I am currently a student of Master of advanced studies in integrated crop management (MAS -ICM) at the university of Neuchâtel, Switzerland supported by CABI. I am writing a thesis on the role of plant doctor quizzes and social media (Plantwise Uganda telegram) in plant health knowledge sharing and transfer in Uganda. I request for your treasured time to fill some questions. The study will provide facts for improvement of digital plant health services. Your responses will remain anonymous. If you have any questions about the survey, please email me: zackzenith@yahoo.com or WhatsApp +256776261998

1. Gender

Mark only one oval.

- Male
- Female

2. Have you been trained by Plantwise?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

3. Have you done a plant doctor quiz?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No (Please go to 4,5,7 & 17)

4. How would you prefer to hear about the plant doctor quiz? (select all that apply, can select more than one)

Check all that apply.

- Facebook
- Email
- WhatsApp
- Plantwise Uganda telegram
- Other:

5. How often would you like to receive the plant doctor quiz?

Mark only one oval.

- Twice a week
- Once a week
- Every after two weeks
- Quarterly (once every 3months).
- Monthly
- Other:

6. Did you put your real name/ any name on the plant doctor quiz?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

7. How comfortable are you with sharing personal information on the plant doctor quiz?

Please select what applies)

Mark only one oval.

- Extremely comfortable
- Very comfortable
- Fairly comfortable
- Not comfortable

8. Have you encouraged others to do the plant doctor quiz?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No (please go to question 10)

9. How did you encourage others to do the plant doctor quiz? (please select all that applies, can select more than one)

Check all that apply.

- Forwarding the quiz link to colleagues
- Advertising the quiz during meetings
- Directly talking to colleagues about the quiz
- Other:

10. Have you ever discussed the answers with your colleagues?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

11. Have you ever started to answer a plant doctor quiz and did not finish? IF YES please, tell us why?

12. Have you ever missed doing a plant doctor quiz? If YES, please tell us why?

13. How much do you agree with the following statements?

Mark only one oval per row.

statements	0. No opinion	1.strongly disagree	2.disagree	3.agree	4.strongly agree
The contents of the plant doctor quiz are interesting and enjoyable to do.					
Plant doctor quiz provide new knowledge					
The contents of the plant doctor quiz increase the diagnostic knowledge & skills					
Knowledge from the quiz can be used to solve pest & disease problems					

14.Overall as a learning tool, plant doctor quiz is:

Mark only one oval.

- 1.poor
- 2. fair
- 3.good
- 4.Excellent

15.Would you like the plant doctor quiz to be longer (more than 10 questions)

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

16.Suggest ways how plant doctor quizzes can be improved

17. Have you ever heard of Plantwise Uganda telegram?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Please go to question 18)
- No

18. Have you subscribed to Plantwise Uganda telegram?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

Appendix 3. Reasons for partial completing of the plant doctor quizzes.

Reasons for partial completing of plant doctor quiz	Frequency	Percent
Loss of internet connection	3	27%
Because of poor internet coverage		
Poor internet connectivity (Network break down)		
Network interruption		
Got engaged with other duties after opening the quiz	5	45%
Opened the quiz and left for other duties,		
Other engagements		
Got engaged with urgent matters		
time factor		
time factor		
Ran out of phone battery	1	9%
Yes, ran out of phone battery.		
Others	2	18%
Yes		
Yes		

Appendix 4. Reasons that Prevented plant doctors from doing plant doctor quizzes (n= 27).

Reasons that Prevented plant doctors from doing plant doctor quizzes	Frequency	Percent
Lack of internet access	6	22%
limited or internet		0%
Yes I was off internet		0%
Lack of internet access		0%
Lack of internet access.		0%
Poor network		0%
Sometimes network disturbs us		0%
Was off Telegram	8	30%
Never received the quiz		0%
I never saw it on time		0%
I was off Plantwise Uganda telegram, i was not receiving on emails		0%
I only received it once.		0%
It was not emailed to me		0%
Was not available		0%
taking too long to check on email		0%
Yes. I changed phones number		0%
Did not respond	5	19%
Yes		0%
Phone battery problems	2	7%

Yes, Battery problems		0%
Yes, my phone was faulty		0%
Busy schedule	7	26%
Yes, when i am very busy in the field		0%
Too busy schedule		0%
Busy work schedule.		0%
Yes, I had no time, I was on the field		0%
Conflicts in schedule		0%
Procrastination		0%
Busy work schedule		0%

Appendix 5. Table showing response on the communication channels through which plant doctors like to hear about the quiz (n=44).

Channel of Communication	Percent	Frequency
Others	2%	1
Facebook	11%	5
Plantwise telegram	59%	26
WhatsApp	64%	28
Email	73%	32

Appendix 6. Table showing response on the Ways how plant doctors encourage others to participate in the quiz (n=44).

Ways how plant doctors encourage others to participate in the quiz	Percent	Frequency
Directly talking to colleagues about the quiz	57%	25
Forwarding the link to colleagues	45%	20
Advertising the quiz during meetings	11%	5
Did not respond	20%	9

Appendix 7. Table shows frequency of use of the different social media types (n=63)

Social media site	(0) Never	(1) Rarely	(2) Often times	(3) Always	Row total
Snapchat	60	1	2	0	63
Whatsapp	11	0	27	25	63
Instagram	47	7	4	5	63
Facebook	21	4	23	15	63
Telegram	30	6	20	7	63

Appendix 8. Table showing reasons that prevent plant doctors from using the Plantwise telegram

What stops you from using telegram as often as possible? (please respond if you subscribe to Plantwise Uganda telegram)
Sometimes I don't have mobile data
Data and OTT
Few subscribers.
Internet data and busy schedule at work
Plant health information is not adequate enough.

My resident has poor network
Ott and data
Data for connecting to the internet.
Data
I changed phone line
Internet access in my area is poor especially to work mates
Often times making accurate diagnosis using shared photos is difficult
Tax on internet: increases the cost of internet and denies accessibility sometimes Poor network connectivity especially in deep rural areas.
sometimes busy work schedules in the field Battery issues: When power is limited or un available, I try to save phone Battery by avoiding using social media
Limitation in terms of internet data
Internet accessibility,OTT
. Most of my contacts are on what's app only and not telegram
poor network in rural areas
Power shortage for charging and data
Network connectivity
Network problem
Funding
Network while in the field, cost..OTT tax
Many times I consult with fellow Plant Doctors and so this reduces how many times i use the telegram platform.
Expensive to buy MBs
Sometimes I lack MBS/ internet connectivity
Expensive data bundles
Daily working nature takes most of the time give little change for operating and accessing telegram, hence mostly have access to it in the evening hours.
Data bundles, low battery and poor net work
Un controlled posting. Some members just keep posting leaving many issues unresolved
Sometimes access to network
Some times they plant doctors take long to give responses to my problem.
Most times queries are not responded to timely
Data bundles and OTT
It's not user friendly and lack of data to often visit the telegram.